

Influence of Yoga on the Reduction of Second Language Anxiety

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Abstract:

In the teaching of English in India, second language anxiety is a prevalent occurrence. Teachers frequently fail to recognize worried pupils and blame bad performance or lack of enthusiasm for their reluctance to participate in speaking assignments. This article's goal is to determine how much yoga can lessen anxiety related to learning a second language. Yoga is a very effective method for reducing stress and anxiety. Three elements make up the practice of yoga: breath control exercises, moderate stretching, and meditation as a mind-body intervention. According to a descriptive study, yoga practice has a significant impact on anxiety related to learning a second language, and there are significant differences between individuals who practice yoga and those who do not.

Keywords: Second Language Anxiety, Yoga, Meditation, Students.

Introduction:

In the present day, English is regarded as the major international language, and the of bilingual users of English will far surpass the number of its native speakers(mckay,2002)1; that is to say, there will be more people who study English as a second or foreign language than English native speakers. English has played a dominant role in the fields of worldwide communication, cultural and academic activities, trading and technology for long decades. It is almost a prerequisite for people to be equipped with above-average English proficiency to be considered competitive for the application of a good job or to be able to absorb huge quantity of information in the academic field. Therefore; English has become one of the most important subjects in the educational system. Aside from the formal learning hours at school, quite a high proportion of parents send their children to cram schools.

As a Second language anxiety learner, anxiety may have stopped you in your tracks. It may have made you fear situations and people you do not know well. It can stop you from making many

important changes in your life. Anxiety can play big tricks on body and mind; excess oxygen levels (produced by breathing too rapidly) can cause muscles to cramp and can cause hyperventilation. Sometimes, the problem is mild but still uncomfortable – for instance, a person may fear having to get up in front of a class and make a speech in another language. The objective of this article is to know how much yoga helps to reduce second language anxiety. After making a descriptive study on it, it is seen that yoga practice leaves an important on second language anxiety, and there is a matters of importance between there who practice yoga and those who do not.

Review:

- 1) Effect of integrated yogic practices on positive and negative emotions in healthy adults. (2011) Lakshmi Narasimhan, R Nagarathna, and HR Nagendra
- 2) Yoga for anxiety: a systematic review of the research Evidence (2011) G Kirkwood, H Rampes, V Tuffrey, J Richardson, K Pilkington
- 3) Harmonious Learning: Yoga in the English Language Classroom (2011) by Lisa Morgan.
- 4) The effect of pranayama on test anxiety and test performance (2013).by Azadeh Nemati

➤ Objective of the study

Every investigation is investigated in the purpose to fulfill some objectives. Thus, this study also has some unique and genuine objectives to achieve. Specific objectives of this study were—

i) How much yoga helps the students to eradicate second language anxiety.

ii) How much difference is there for learning second language among the students of class VIII who practice yoga regularly and who do not practice it.

iii) What the performance is in the case of second language of students who practice yoga regularly.

➤ Hypothesis of the study:

- ✓ H_1 : There would be no significance different between practice yoga boys & girls and non practice yoga boys and girls in second language anxiety.
- ✓ H_2 : There would be no significance difference between practice yoga boys and non practice yoga boys in second language anxiety.
- ✓ H_3 : There would be no significance different between practice yoga girls and non practice yoga girls in second language anxiety.

➤ **Nature of the present study:** Nature of the present study is “**Descriptive**”

➤ **Sampling & population of the study:** The researcher selected the some class VIII rural school students in Malda district for his research population.

➤ **Population of the study:** All the class viii students “Influence of yoga on the reduction of second language anxiety in Malda district.

➤ Sampling of the study:

For the selection of the sample in the present study, the investigator used the multistage random sampling technique. First of all, the investigator collected the list of secondary schools in Malda district, affiliated to West Bengal board of higher secondary education, from the official web- side of the Government of west Bengal school education department. With the help of that list, the schools were selected randomly. There were the researcher selected hundred students in class VIII randomly selected from these schools of Malda districts. From these students, male and female

students are listed separately. From that list, a total sample of 100 students where 100 students from rural (male-50 & female-50).

➤ Sampling:

The research selected the 2 schools on Malda district and gives 100 samples. School were-

a) Mozampur HSSB High School. (H.S)

b) Mohammadia High Madrasah (H.S)

Name of school	Nature of school	Locality	No. of Sample collected		Total
			Male	Female	
Mozampur HSSB High School.(H.S)	Rural co-ed	Kaliachak (malda)	25	25	50
Mohammadia High Madrasah (H.S)	Rural co-ed	Kaliachak (malda)	25	25	50

Yoga practice boys & girls student and non-practice yoga boys & girls students table:

Name of school	Yoga practice boys & girls student		Non-practice yoga boys & girls students	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
Mozampur HSSB High School. (H.S)	14	12	11	13
Mohammadia High Madrasah (H.S)	13	11	12	14

➤ Tools

The researcher further delimited his study in the construction of a standardized tool for measuring the Influence of yoga on the reduction of second language anxiety of the students.

➤ Procedure of the Data Collection

First of all, before the collection of data, the investigator contacted the Head Masters of the selected schools of Malda district to take permission for data collection, by explaining the purpose of the study. They were assured that the data would be used for research purpose only and the responses would be kept confidential. After getting permission of the Head masters and winning the co-operation of the teachers, all possible efforts were made to ensure the best possible conditions for administering the test and to make the students feel at ease and respond to the test with full concentration. In ordered to conduct the study the students of Second Language Anxiety were identified and the test (Likert attitude scale) was administered to these students in the formal atmosphere of the schools, one after the other. Before the administration of particular test, the important instructions regarding how to answer the questions were read out loudly and clearly by the investigator.

➤ Analysis and Interpretation of the Data:

The interpretation of data is of great importance in the field of research. The data as such has no meaning if it is not analyzed and interpreted properly. So the next step in the process of research, after the collection of data is the organization, analysis and interpretation of data and gets a meaningful picture out of the raw information collected. At first, the comparison between different groups on academic performance has been shown. In this chapter the investigator presents, analyses and interprets the collected data.

➤ Representation of Descriptive data

Presentation of descriptive statistics of second language anxiety & yoga scores of total sample, group samples.

Table-1: Here the below table show the value of Mean, Median, Mode and S.D of class VIII students.

Categories	Mean	Median	Mode	S.D
Boys practice yoga	66.62	64.91	58.89	8.66
Girls practice yoga	57.59	59.27	62.63	2.91
Boys non-practice yoga	58.58	61.59	67.61	3.32
Girls non-practice yoga	54.87	55	55.26	6.19
All boys & girls practice yoga.	61.5	60.16	57.48	9.65
All boys & girls non-practice yoga.	56.5	57.5	59.5	3.79

➤ Representation of Inferential statistics:

- ✓ H_1 : There would be no significance different between practice yoga boys & girls and non practice yoga boys and girls in second language anxiety.

Table- 2: Showing means difference between boys and girls students in their practice yoga boys & girls and non practice yoga boys and girls in second language anxiety.

Group	N	Mean	S.D	T- value	Level of significance
Practice boys & girls	50	61.5	9.65	3.42	Significant at 0.05 level
Non- practice boys & girls	50	56.5	3.79		

The calculate value $Z=3.42$ and $df = 98$ which is in given problem. From table-2, the critical value at 0.05 level is 1.98, similarly the 0.01 level is 2.63, Therefore the critical value is smaller than the calculate value. So the null hypothesis is rejected and the relation is significant.

Hence the yoga practice boys & girls and yoga non practice boys & girls relation was a significant difference about influence of yoga on the reduction of Second Language Anxiety is proved.

- ✓ H_2 : There would be no significance difference between practice yoga boys and non practice yoga boys in second language anxiety.

Table- 3: Showing means difference between practice yoga boys and non practice yoga boys in second language anxiety.

Group	N	Mean	S.D	T- value	Level of significance
Practice yoga boys	27	66.62	8.66	2.79	Significant at 0.05 level
Non- practice yoga boys	23	61.59	3.32		

The calculate value $Z=2.79$ and $df = 48$ which is in given problem. From table-3, the critical value at 0.05 level is 2.01, similarly the 0.01 level is 2.68, Therefore the critical value is smaller than the calculate value. So the null hypothesis is rejected and the relation is significant.

Hence the yoga practice boys and yoga non practice boys relation was a significant difference about influence of yoga on the reduction of Second Language Anxiety is proved.

✓ H_3 : There would be no significance different between practice yoga girls and non practice yoga girls in second language anxiety.

Table- 4: Showing means difference between practice yoga girls and non practice yoga girls in second language anxiety.

Group	N	Mean	S.D	T- value	Level of significance
Practice yoga girls	23	57.59	2.91	2.04	Significant at 0.05 level
Non- practice yoga girls	27	54.87	6.19		

The calculate value $Z=2.04$ and $df = 48$ which is in given problem. From table-4, the critical value at 0.05 level is 2.01, similarly the 0.01 level is 2.68, Therefore the critical value is smaller than the calculate value. So the null hypothesis is rejected and the relation is significant.

Hence the yoga practice girls and yoga non practice girls relation was a significant difference about influence of yoga on the reduction of Second Language Anxiety is proved.

Conclusion:

English anxiety is a problem for many people. It can have detrimental effects for schools students including felling of nervous tension. Fair of rejection and stress, English anxiety in children is a learned response from the attitudes of present and educators alike. Parents and educators must change their respective of English skill in a positive way. By embracing English as an essential tool for success in our society. These adult can help create a new view point among students to ward skills that are so fundamental to so many aspects of life. English educators to recognize the cause of English anxiety.

From the discussion I think English anxiety is a burden to the student to learn English. It may affect the future of the student. From this research I come to know that yoga can help the students to bring down their English anxiety. Collection of data and statistically calculation clearly prove that yoga practicing students and yoga-non practicing students are not same in English anxiety. They differ from each other. Yoga practicing students can learn English more quickly than non-practicing students. If each student can be practiced yoga it will helped them to learn English more quickly and they make their future life good and well established.

Main Findings:

- 1) The calculate value exists on the critical value in (Table-2) the null hypothesis is rejected and the relation is significant. In the study the practice yoga boys & girls and non practice yoga boys and girls relation exists a significant difference in Second Language Anxiety.
- 2) The calculate value exists on the critical value in (Table-3) the null hypothesis is rejected and the relation is significant. In the study the practice yoga boys and non practice yoga boys relation exists a significant difference in Second Language Anxiety.

3) The calculate value exists on the critical value in (Table-4) the null hypothesis is rejected and the relation is significant. In the study the practice yoga girls and non practice yoga girls relation exists a significant difference in Second Language Anxiety.

References:

1. Abu-Rabia, S. (2004). "Teachers' role, learners' gender differences, and FL anxiety among seventh-grade students studying English as a FL." *Educational Psychology* 24(5): 711-720.
2. Aida Y (1994) Examination of Horwitz, Horwitz and Coe's construct of foreign language anxiety: The case of students of Japanese. *The Modern Language J.* 78, 155-168.
3. Brown R and Gerbag P (2005) Sudarshan Kriya yogic beathing in the treatment of stress, anxiety and depression. *The J. Alt. & Complementary Med.* 2(4), 711-717.
4. MacIntyre PD and Gardner RC (1991) Language anxiety: Its relation to other anxieties and to processing in native and second languages.
5. *Language Learning.* 41(58), 117.
6. MacIntyre PD and Gardner RC (1993) On the measurement of affective variables in second language learning. *Language Learning.* 43, 157-194.
7. Poppleton CA (2011) Language learners and anxiety: Breathing technique for self-calming. *TESOL Connections.*

Websites

Yoga Journal

www.Yogajournal.com: Free podcasts and an index of poses

The Yoga Site

www.Yogasite.com/postures: Downloadable simple stick figures and directions for poses